

Removal of phenol and penta-chloro-phenol from water by liquid-liquid extraction using reverse micelles[†]

Geetika Gupta, Aarti Raman and Suddhasatwa Basu*

Department of Chemical Engineering, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi, New Delhi-110 016, India

E-mail : sbasu@iitd.ac.in

Abstract : In the present work, solvent extraction using reverse micelles is proposed for the removal of penta-chloro-phenol (PCP) from water. In this approach, the PCP is solubilized in the aqueous core of the reverse micelles, which are present in the organic phase. The organic phase is subsequently separated from the aqueous phase leading to significant removal of PCP. Experimental results reveal that the electrostatic interaction between the oppositely charged surfactant head group present in the reverse micelles and the PCP molecule plays a key role in the separation. The removal of the anionic PCP from water is carried out in the presence of cationic hexadecyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (HTAB) surfactant. Xylene is used as the solvent. The influence of parameters such as solute concentrations, surfactant concentrations, volume of the solvent on the percentage removal of PCP are studied. The percentage removal of PCP is decreased with the increase in PCP concentration in the feed. The percentage removal of PCP reaches a maximum when the critical concentration of the surfactant is used and it decreases on going on either side from the critical value.

Keywords : Reverse micelles, phenol, pentachlorophenol, liquid-liquid extraction, water purification.

Introduction

The contamination of soils, sludges, and bodies of 'fresh' water by chlorinated organic compounds is a serious world-wide hazardous waste problem. The effluent water from wood preservative and insecticide industry contains penta-chloro-phenol, DDT, hexa-chloro-phenol, lindane and many other chlorinated solvents. These must be removed before discharging the effluent to the environment to avoid health hazards. The investigation on the removal of such chemicals has been going on for several years. In this project we are mainly dealing with the removal of penta-chloro-phenol (PCP) from waste water¹. Not much has been done in this field before.

PCP is used in the pressure treatment of lumber to protect it from fungal rot and wood-boring insects. It may also be used as a pre-harvest defoliant in cotton, a general pre-emergence herbicide, and as a biocide in industrial water systems. Thus it finds its way into both soil and water. PCP dissolves to the extent of 1.20 mg/ml in water at room temperature so that one can expect that this contaminant will be present in lakes and streams¹.

PCP is highly toxic, regardless of the route, length, and frequency of exposure. Lethal doses induce an increased respiratory rate, a marked rise in temperature, tremors, and a loss of righting reflex. PCP is also an irritant for exposed epithelial tissue, especially the mucosal tissues of the eyes, nose, and throat. Other localized acute effects include swelling, skin damage, and hair loss, as well as flushed skin areas where PCP affects surface blood vessels. PCP, usually at much lower concentrations, can decrease growth rates, increase the weights of liver, lungs, kidneys, and adrenals, increase the activity of a number of liver enzymes, interfere with porphyrin metabolism, alter haematological and biochemical parameters, and interfere with renal function.

Conventional chemical engineering techniques have been found to be inadequate and not cost effective in the removal of PCP from water¹. Special filters can be used to adsorb the soluble contaminant, for example filtration through a bed of granular activated charcoal. A PCP contaminated water solution can be remediated by filtering it under vacuum through a plug of clean unacidified soil.

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

This method is effective only to an extent because degree of extraction is less and PCP recovery is not possible. PCP forms an unextractable complex with soil and we are left with the problem of contaminated filters.

Conventional methods for extracting phenol include using methylisobutylketone as an extracting agent and separation through distillation. A novel method using colloidal gas aphrons (CGA) is proposed by Roy *et al.*² for the separation of organic dyes from water. CGA is a gas bubble encapsulated in a thin, aqueous, soapy shell. CGAs are used in a flotation column to remove dyes from water³. Chapalkar *et al.*⁴ showed the use of CGA to remove PCP from contaminated water. The successful use of CGAs for the removal of chloro phenols by encapsulating in the soapy shell led to the idea of the use of reverse micelles for the removal of dyes in a similar manner. The CGA method is found to be inefficient as compared to the present method described here (i.e. solvent extraction using reverse micelles).

The usage of liquid-liquid extraction using reverse micelles will not only increase the percentage remediation but also help us recover PCP for its further applications as listed above. However, large bodies of water contaminated with PCP can not be processed using method since it may not be economical viable. In such case precipitation may be a better option as far as economics of the process is concerned.

Surfactants have long been playing an important role in a wide variety of industries. They are amphiphilic molecules containing a non-polar hydrophobic tail, usually a straight or branched hydrocarbon chain at one end, and a polar hydrophilic group which can be nonionic, zwitterionic or ionic at the another end. As a result of the solvophobic association, these molecules are capable of forming a rich variety of structurally organized assemblies such as micelles and reversed micelles. Reverse micelles are nanometer size aggregates of surfactant molecules surrounding a microscopic water core in apolar solvents. These inverted aggregates are drawn together by hydrogen bonding in the presence of minimal amounts of water and they are thermodynamically stable. The effect of different parameters, e.g. PCP concentrations, surfactant concentrations, and amount of solvent on efficiency of removal of PCP from water is studied.

The purpose of the present study is to investigate the

application of reverse micelles in removing organic PCP from water by liquid-liquid extraction following work of Pandit and Basu⁵⁻⁷. To investigate the influence of various process parameters like nature of solvent, surfactant and their concentrations on the percentage removal of phenol and PCP from water. To determine the correct concentration of surfactant to be used for extraction verify the results using COD removal technique.

Experimental

Materials :

The surfactant used to prepare reverse micelles is hexadecyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (HTAB). HTAB (mol. wt. 364.6) is a cationic surfactant having a cmc (Critical Micelles Concentration) of 350 mg/L. The structure of HTAB is $\text{CH}_3-(\text{CH}_2)_{15}-\text{NC}(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{Br}$. The solvent used for PCP removal from water is xylene. The details are available in reference⁵. Freshly prepared distilled water is used in all the experiments.

Experimental setup :

The schematic view of the experimental setup is given in Refs. [5,6]. A simple stirrer is used for the mixing of the solvent and the aqueous phase. The rpm of the stirrer can be measured accurately. The impeller used is a three-bladed axial type. A separating funnel, which is connected to the mixer, is used to separate the solvent and aqueous phases by gravity. UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu) was used to analyze the PCP removal. COD removal was measured using Thermo-Fischer photometer comparing with standard COD samples.

Methods :

One hundred milliliters of aqueous solution containing a given quantity of phenol and PCP is prepared (since PCP is only slightly soluble in water, it has to be dissolved in phenol before solubilizing it in water). A known quantity of cationic surfactant (HTAB) is added to 25 ml of xylene. A small quantity (almost 10% of the volume of the solvent) of octanol is added to the solvent phase as a co-surfactant to increase the effectiveness of xylene. The aqueous phase and the solvent phase (xylene) are mixed thoroughly using the stirrer at 150 rpm for 10 min. The two-phase dispersion is transferred to a separating funnel to separate the solvent and aqueous phases by gravity. The heavier aqueous phase is collected at the bottom of the separating funnel, whereas the lighter xylene is col-

lected at the top. Samples collected from the bottom aqueous phase (remaining PCP and phenol) are diluted with a known volume of distilled water. The diluted PCP and phenol sample is analyzed to determine the amount of PCP separated. The dilution effect of the aqueous phase solution is taken into account while estimating the percentage removal of PCP and phenol from water. The experiments are repeated to check the accuracy and the data are found to be accurate within a 5% error except for a few instances⁶.

Xylene is sparingly soluble in water at room temperature and atmospheric pressure. Experimentally it has been found out that xylene is the best for the removal of PCP from water using the reverse micelles technique. To succeed as a viable alternative to the conventional extraction process, the reverse micellar extraction technique must use a solvent, which is easily and cost effectively separated from solvent/aqueous phase dispersion in the presence of surfactant⁶. The other important criterion is that the reverse micelles should form in the solvent phase. The dispersion of xylene in water is easy to separate into pure phases in a separating funnel by gravity compared to other solvents tested, e.g. amyl alcohol, hexanol, etc. The samples of aqueous phase are tested, after gravity separation, for phenol concentration either by the direct photometric method or COD removal method.

Direct photometric method :

First a calibration chart is prepared by recording the absorbance of the solution for different phenol and PCP concentrations using Shimadzu spectrophotometer equipped with absorption cells providing light paths of 1 to 5 cm for use at 500 nm. For finding out the concentration of the unknown sample, absorbance is determined experimentally and then the corresponding value of phenol concentration is read from the graph. The absorbency spectra analysis indicated that the maximum absorbencies is at 500 nm.

Following solutions were used in photometric method experiments. Phosphate buffer solution prepared by dissolving 104.5 g K_2HPO_4 and 72.3 g KH_2PO_4 in water and diluted to 1 L at a pH 6.8 was used. 4-Aminoantipyrine solution was prepared by dissolving 2.0 g 4-aminoantipyrine in water and diluted to 100 ml. Potassium ferricyanide solution was prepared using 8.0 g $K_3Fe(CN)_6$ in water and diluted to 100 ml. Filter if necessary and

store in a brown bottle. Prepare fresh weekly.

Chemical oxygen demand :

Chemical oxygen demand is used as a measure of oxygen requirement of a sample that is susceptible to oxidation by strong chemical oxidant. Chemical oxygen demand (COD) is a vital test for assessing the quality of effluents and waste waters prior to discharge. The COD test predicts the oxygen requirement of the effluent and is used for the monitoring and control of discharges, and for assessing treatment plant performance. The standard test for COD involves digesting the sample with strong sulphuric acid solution in the presence of chromium and silver salts.

The COD of the samples is determined using special tubes. The reagents are available pre-mixed and pre-dispersed into borosilicate glass test tubes, which reduces contact with potentially hazardous chemicals to a minimum. The chemical composition of the oxidizing reagent is potassium dichromate ($K_2Cr_2O_7$) of 0.25 N, sulphuric acid (H_2SO_4) and silver sulphate (Ag_2SO_4) solution, mercuric sulphate ($HgSO_4$) crystals, ferrous ammonium sulphate (FAS) [$Fe(NH_4)_2(SO_4)_2$] of ~0.01 N and ferroin indicator (1,10-phenanthroline and ferrous ammonium sulphate). These potentially hazardous chemicals clearly need to be handled with extreme care. The test is carried out by adding 2 ml of the sample to the tube containing above solution, closing the cap and then digesting for two hours at 150 °C. The tubes are then cooled (for about an hour) and the test color measured using a photometer. The set up is first calibrated using a blank and a standard. The standard solution is prepared by adding 0.429 g of potassium hydrogen phthalate (of 99% potential) to 500 ml water. This solution has a COD of 500.

Results and discussion

Effect of surfactant concentrations :

The surfactant is an indispensable component in the reverse micelle extraction process since the phenol is removed by solubilizing it in the self-assembly of surfactant molecules. The increase in the surfactant concentration gives greater opportunity to a large number of phenol molecules to solubilize in the reverse micelles. However, the increase in the surfactant concentration may lead to stable aqueous-solvent phase dispersion resulting in poor separation of phases. Thus the surfactant mole-

cule plays both a positive and a negative role in the removal of phenol through reverse micelles route. Thus it is desirable to evaluate the required amount of surfactant needed for a given amount of phenol removal. It can be seen from the graph that the percentage removal is maximum at the CMC (350 mg/L). It decreases on going on either side of the critical value.

The xylene has a fixed capacity for encapsulating phenol molecules for a given surfactant concentration since the number of reverse micelles formed is constant. Thus, the percentage removal of phenol decreases with the increase in phenol concentration. An enhanced capacity of xylene for phenol encapsulation is achieved by increasing the surfactant concentration and, consequently, increasing the number of reverse micelles^{5,6}. Therefore, the increase in surfactant concentration leads to the increase in reverse micelle concentration, which in turn yields higher removal of phenol from water.

Experiments were also performed using Tergitol (non-ionic) as surfactant. Not much difference was found in the percentage extraction. This is because the percentage extraction depends only on the number of reverse mi-

Fig. 1. Percentage removal of phenol with surfactant (HTAB) and without surfactant in 50 ml of the solvent (xylene).

Fig. 2. Percentage removal of phenol with surfactant (HTAB) and without surfactant in 25 ml of xylene.

Fig. 3. Percentage removal of phenol with surfactant (HTAB) and without surfactant in 10 ml of xylene.

Fig. 4. Change in percentage removal of phenol with change in concentration of surfactant. The percentage extraction is maximum at CMC (350 mg/L of HTAB in water).

Fig. 5. Percentage extraction of phenol using Tergitol and HTAB as surfactants in xylene solvents.

celles formed in the solvent phase. Equal concentrations of different types of surfactants generate equal number of reverse micelles and hence approximately equal amount of percentage extraction is obtained. However, PCP being anionic in nature, an anionic surfactant should not be used because reverse micelles are formed as a result of electrostatic interaction between oppositely charged surfactant and solute molecules.

Gupta *et al.* : Removal of phenol and penta-chloro-phenol from water by liquid-liquid extraction *etc.*

Fig. 6. Percentage extraction of phenol with surfactant (HTAB) and without surfactant using 50 ml of iso-amyl alcohol as solvent.

Fig. 7. Graph showing change in percentage removal of phenol with increase in volume of solvent (xylene) from 10 ml to 25 ml to 50 ml.

Fig. 8. Percentage COD removal with change in HTAB conc. in 25 ml xylene. The PCP is solubilised in 1 ml of phenol before adding in 100 ml water.

Effect of solvent :

The effect of the nature of solvent on the removal of phenol is studied by deducing the percentage removal in the absence of surfactant from that in the presence of surfactant. The removal of phenol in the absence of surfactants occurs due to solubility of phenol in the solvent.

Fig. 9 shows the effect of surfactant when iso-amyl alcohol is used as a solvent. The percentage removal in the absence of surfactant is only slightly less than the

percentage removal in presence of surfactant, when iso-amyl is used as a solvent. This is because of similar nature of functional group present i.e. alcoholic group, phenol dissolves out of aqueous layer into the solvent phase. As a result, a large percentage of phenol separates even in absence of surfactant. Fig. 10 shows the effect of increasing solvent volume. The percentage removal of phenol increases with increase in volume of the solvent even in the absence of surfactant. On the other hand when iso-octane or xylene is used as the solvent, there is large difference in the percentage extraction when surfactant is used. The presence of certain straight chain aliphatic alcohols called *co-surfactants* like hexanol, heptanol, octanol further increases the percentage extraction. A co-surfactant increases the effectiveness of another surfactant. Straight chain aliphatic alcohol (number of carbon atom in the alcohol ≥ 5) can act as co-surfactants. Introduction of them into the polymeric reversed solution significantly affects reversed micelle formation, micelle diameter and the extraction equilibrium.

Phase separation :

The separation of aqueous and solvent phase is an important issue for the practical implementation of phenol removal by liquid-liquid extraction using reverse micelles. The advantage and disadvantage of the presence of surfactant in phenol surfactant is already discussed in the previous section. The time required to separate a fraction of clear aqueous phase increase with the increase in surfactant concentration. Thus, an optimum surfactant concentration should be used for phenol removal by reverse micelles such that the phase separation time is not high as well as the percentage removal is not low.

To succeed as a viable alternative to the conventional phenol removal processes, the reverse micelles concentration should use a solvent that is easily and cost-effectively separated from solvent-aqueous phase dispersion in the presence of surfactant. The other important criterion is that reverse micelles should form in the solvent phase. The dispersion of xylene in water is easy to separate into pure phases by gravity a cylindrical column.

COD removal :

COD measures the purity of water in the context of water pollution control. Fig. 11 shows the COD of water after treating with liquid-liquid extraction process using

reverse micelles decreases significantly as compared to original phenol solution. It has been found that COD of 100 ml solution of a 500 ppm solution of phenol decreases significantly from 7590 to 1612 on extraction with 25 ml of xylene containing 350 mg/L of HTAB. The percentage removal generally increases on increasing the surfactant concentration. However, the extra addition of surfactant in the solvent phase increases the COD level of water due to transfer of some minute amount of surfactant to the aqueous phase. Therefore, the amount of surfactant to be used for the reverse-micellar extraction has to be chosen very carefully. However, the solvents are primarily present in the solvent phase in the form of reverse micelles. Therefore, the COD removal from the aqueous phase increases with increase in the surfactant concentration since a large amount of PCP is removed (which is evident from the graph). The percentage of COD removal increases from almost 20% in the absence of surfactant to more than 80% when surfactant is added to the solvent phase. The breaking of reverse micelles and re-use of surfactants and recovery of concentrated amount of extract phase is discussed elaborately by Pandit and Basu⁷.

PCP removal mechanism :

The PCP molecules react with surfactant head groups to form complexes. In the present model, one molecule of the PCP reacts with one molecule of the oppositely charged surfactant to form a PCP-surfactant complex, which further dissociates to release the counter ion in the water pool of the reverse micelle. The solubilisation depends on identification of the specific ion-exchange reactions. Since phenol is slightly soluble in some of the solvents, the solubility of phenol in absence of surfactants is accounted. There are essentially four distinct regions in a reverse micellar system where a PCP molecule may be present. They are as follows : (i) the bulk of the organic phase; (ii) the interface between the surfactant hydrophilic head group and the water pool of the reverse micelles; (iii) the water pool inside the reverse micelles and (iv) the bulk of the aqueous phase. The removal of phenol from the aqueous phase without using surfactant is very low compared to the percentage removal using surfactant. Fig. 4 shows the comparison of the removal of phenol in the presence and absence of HTAB surfactant. In the absence of surfactant, the removal of phenol from

water to xylene follows a conventional solvent extraction process.

It can be seen in Fig. 4 that the conventional solvent extraction method (0 mg HTAB) yields less percentage removal of phenol. The percentage removal of phenol increases drastically in the presence of HTAB surfactant due to encapsulation of phenol in the reverse micelles formed in xylene. It should be noted that a clear xylene and aqueous phases were obtained after the mixing and separation of pure phases.

Conclusion

Removal of PCP and phenol of 60–70% from the aqueous phase is possible by encapsulating PCP in reverse micelles formed by surfactant in solvent. PCP is removed from water by forming reverse micelles of cationic HTAB surfactants in xylene. Octanol is used as a co-surfactant to increase the percentage extraction. A small quantity of phenol and PCP is transferred to xylene when no surfactant is used. Experimental results show that with proper control of different parameters such as dye, surfactant, the percentage removal of PCP from water can be increased. The effect of different parameters are percentage removal of phenol decreases with an increase in phenol concentration, percentage removal of phenol increases with an increase in surfactant concentration. Thus, feed having a high concentration of phenol can be handled by using a high concentration of surfactant. These results are explained based on charge transfer mechanisms, electrostatic interactions and PCP-surfactant complex formation.

References

1. R. A. Abramovitch and M. Capracotta, *Chemosphere*, 2003, **50**, 955.
2. D. Roy, K. T. Valsaraj and S. A. Kottai, *Sep. Sci. Technol.*, 1992, **27**, 573.
3. P. R. Malpani and S. Basu, *Sep. Sci. Technol.*, 2001, **36**, 2997.
4. P. G. Chaphalkar, K. T. Valsraj and D. Roy, *Sep. Sci. Technol.*, 1994, **29**, 907.
5. P. Pandit and S. Basu, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2002, **245**, 208.
6. P. Pandit and S. Basu, *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2004, **38**, 2435.
7. P. Pandit and S. Basu, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.*, 2004, **43**, 7861.